

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Postolenko Iryna

PhD, associate professor

English and Methodology Department

Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University

26 Sadova Street, Uman, Cherkasy Region, Ukraine

Abstract

The issue of age and individual characteristics in the preparation of foreign languages remains insufficiently studied. Although foreign language training continues throughout school life, in some cases from kindergarten through high school, the level of foreign language training is generally insufficient for practical use in human life. One of the reasons for this situation, in our opinion, is the insufficient consideration of the age and individual characteristics of students in the process of learning foreign languages.

Keywords: individual characteristics, high school students, foreign languages, learning, cognitive process, development, holistic thinking, perception.

One of the main issues of the theory of individual human development is the question of the relationship between age, typological and individual characteristics of a person, about the contradictory and changing relationships between them. Their unique combination will become the basis for the development of the psyche in specific areas, thereby contributing to the manifestation and development of the ability to master academic disciplines, especially a foreign language. With the change of age, in the school period, the value of verbal memory, memorization of figurative meanings increases, creative thinking starts to play an important role, the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships is revealed, also speech and mental activity become more differentiated. The success of learning foreign languages at different ages is determined by the predominance of different components in the structure of language skills. At the initial stage of training, the successful mastery of foreign languages is mainly related to the superiority of personal parameters; at higher stages of training, cognitive and psychophysiological indicators are mainly determined. At the same time, personal factors are not sufficiently used in high school [1, p. 6].

Psychologists attribute the age of high school students (15-18) to early adolescence. Early adolescence exists between childhood and adulthood. This age is characterized by a number of psychological features. Currently, the age specificity of this period of development is almost certainly different, which is reflected in all aspects of learning and school life of high school students. A modern high school student is a product of modern life, complex, interesting and contradictory at the same time. A person's physical maturation is completed in high school age. The physical development of modern 17-year-old students corresponds to the development of 22-year-old students in the 1930s [1, p. 7].

In early adolescence, qualitative changes occur in all aspects of mental activity. Perception becomes arbitrary, manifests itself in perceptual acts of systematic

observation of certain objects, one's own actions, behavior, experiences and thoughts. The memory of high school students undergoes significant changes: long-term verbal and logical memory prevails in them, the arbitrariness of memory increases, the productivity of logical memorization increases, and the means of memorization are improved. Productivity of involuntary memory also depends on the organization of mental activity, the role of which does not diminish. We involuntarily remember, first of all, what is connected with the interests and needs of high school students, with their plans for the future. Let us consider in more detail the components of the cognitive processes of high school students and their influence on learning foreign languages [2]. One of the important aspects of the intellectual development of high school students is intensive intellectual maturation, in which developmental thinking plays a leading role. The center of cognitive development of high school students is the formation of verbal and logical thinking. There is a transition to higher levels of abstract and generalizing thinking. Scientific concepts become not only a subject of research, but also a tool of knowledge.

Students of this age are able to consciously master logical operations (analysis, synthesis, comparison, reflection, abstraction, concretization, and generalization). They form an individual cognitive style of solving cognitive and practical tasks, develop individual features of thinking, including: depth, flexibility, breadth, awareness, independence, criticality, etc. The thinking of different students of the same age differs in the ratio of visual-figurative and verbal-logical components, as well as the level of productivity. Especially in the process of learning a foreign language, the specificity of students' thinking affects the speed of forming verbal connections and functional language generalizations, the flexibility of transformational processes, etc. Depending on the level of development of the student's productive thinking and the nature of the educational

goal, the teacher should direct his thinking from concrete to abstract and vice versa. Thus, the presence of individual differences in thinking requires different methods of teaching foreign languages. Since high school students are characterized by synthesis in relation to a high abstract-logical form of thinking, this (synthesis) causes the appearance of critical features in their analytical activity, the desire to discuss issues that concern them. It follows from this that the structure of the communication content of foreign language lessons should be problematic [3, p. 34].

With the development of abstract and holistic thinking, high school students reach higher levels of language proficiency. As the thinking of young boys and girls develops, the content and structure of their speech becomes more complex. Active and passive vocabulary expands. Oral and written expression improves. There is a transition from an expanded internal language to a shortened (concise) internal one, which becomes the basis of mental action. High school students are characterized by significantly higher communicative development than elementary school students.

They have a more perfect command of morphological and syntactic aspects of speech, coherence, logic and sequence of utterances. The statement demonstrates the ability to analyze, compare, generalize, draw conclusions, and predict. All this implies, on the one hand, the need to have adequate linguistic material, as well as the use of authentic written and acoustic texts in the educational process. On the other hand, there is a need for new, undeveloped language skills at previous levels of education, which ensure the implementation of a normative and generalizing function, for example, the ability to communicate in an organizational form of discussion. Since the unit of teaching foreign languages today is not a word or a sentence, but a text, during the teaching of foreign languages, an analogy with the process of learning a native language is allowed and the circle of interests and cognitive needs is expanded [5, p. 95].

Memory plays an equally important role in the acquisition of foreign languages, as does speech. In early adolescence, students develop a desire to master their memory and manage it, to increase productivity. It should be noted that memorization is not reduced to understanding, but requires specific methods of memorization and reproduction and consolidation of consciously learned information. Learning material first enters short-term memory and then must be transferred to long-term memory through exercises. Both types of memory are of great importance for language activity. The main trend in the development of the memory of a high school student is characterized by its increase and strengthening of willpower. As psychologists note, random memorization prevails among high school students, which is effective when they realize the necessity and expediency of memorizing this or that material, as well as the effectiveness of the final result [4, p. 28]. Memorizing the material will help to understand the characteristic features of this material, to recognize the relationship and meaningful grouping of the objects of memorization and to focus on intensive work.

It is characteristic that boys and girls of this age are more self-critical than teenagers. This circumstance makes it possible to better organize work on the elimination of defects according to individual tasks. At a higher level, the combination of forms of individual, pair and team work (the latter predominates), where the teacher acts as a partner, organizer, animator, director, screenwriter, director, etc., becomes more and more important. At the same time, the group is given a general cognitive task, and the teacher organizes and stimulates joint research, where everyone performs their work task. It is necessary to deal with the understanding and calculation of the phenomenon characteristic of this age - the desire of the schoolboy to attract more attention from others. A foreign language teacher can use it when organizing discussions, setting tasks in role-playing games or project work, when developing individual tasks and organizing self-help, when setting individual tasks for organizing extracurricular work [6, p. 29].

In high school age, involuntary memory acquires a specific character, the role of which cannot be underestimated. The productivity of this memory also depends on the mental work of students during the learning process. In particular, they remember learning material better if it is part of the goal of their intellectual activity. High school students better involuntarily remember what is an obstacle and difficulties in their success. In addition, the involuntary recall of what is related to the needs, desires and interests of students, their plans for the future, causes a strong emotional reaction in them. For this type of memory, reflective methods and methods of working with educational materials in foreign language classes are especially relevant (reference outline, algorithm, sync-way, intelligence map, cluster, etc.) [5, p. 51].

The development of the cognitive sphere of high school students also consists in improving the ability to direct attention to specific subjects and phenomena, overcoming the influence of distracting factors. All this indicates the development of concentration. The volume, stability, degree of focus, speed of attention switching increase. The development of these qualities of attention is connected with the development of logical thinking. But the selectivity of attention also increases, its dependence on the direction of interest, the role of post-voluntary attention increases. Although involuntary attention, which is usually dictated by the student's immediate interest, cannot be forgotten, it requires special attention when teaching foreign languages [5, p. 52].

The development of the imagination of high school students is marked by the disclosure of their inner world. The assimilation of the material becomes much more difficult and requires the activation of reproductive and creative imagination. Students observe a more critical attitude towards the creations of their own imagination; they strengthen self-control over the work being performed. The development of senior schoolchildren's perception is manifested by the predominance of its arbitrary form, the assimilation of perceptual actions, the deliberate observation of certain objects, the identification of the essence in objects,

events and phenomena. This is especially characteristic for the perception of complex materials, grammatical phenomena and regularities.

There is a development of integrity, meaningfulness, objectivity, selectivity, and especially perception. A holistic image is created on the basis of a conscious generalization of data about individual properties, features and functions of the object, as a result of the integration of experiences of different modalities. The given psychological characteristics of high school students are of a general nature. Ignoring them can lead to negative consequences. The general is always realized in a special way in the individual and therefore has a peculiarity in the individual case. Recognition and acceptance of this uniqueness is no less important than the development of general rules and norms. This applies, in particular, to a foreign language, which belongs to a group of active educational disciplines, the purpose of which is primarily the development of specific skills and abilities.

References

1. Butkivska P. Psychological readiness of high school students to communicate in a foreign language. Native school. 2017. No. 2. P.6-8. [Published in Ukrainian]
2. Herlun N. Peculiarities of motivation for learning a foreign language by high school students. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: http://fp.nsk.fio.ru/works/022/mpi/psikol_2_2.htm (date of access 11.10.2023) [Published in Ukrainian]
3. Zhytnyk B. Methodical adviser. Forms and methods of education. Kharkiv: Osнова, 2018. 128 p. [Published in Ukrainian]
4. Kozachuk S. The structure of schoolchildren's cognitive activity in the process of learning a foreign language. Scientific notes of the H.S. Kostyuk Institute of Psychology of the Academy of Sciences of Ukraine Edited by Academician S. D. Maksimenko. Kyiv: Millennium, 2016. Vol. 27. P.277-287. [Published in Ukrainian]
5. Matiushkin O. The problem of motivation for learning a foreign language and the linguistic and cultural aspect. Foreign languages. 2018. No. 522. P.10-12.
6. Chernysh V. Age features of high school students. Foreign languages. 2017. No. 3. P.15-22. [Published in Ukrainian]